

Synthesis of 2-Aryl Amino-5-Aryl/Aryloxy Methyl-1,3,4-Oxadiazoles, 2-Aryl Amino-5-Aryl/Aryloxy Methyl-1,3,4-Thiadiazoles, N₁-Aryl/Aryloxy Acetyl-3,5-Dimethyl Pyrazoles and N₁-Aryl/Aryloxy Acetyl-3-Methyl-5-Pyrazolones as Possible Fungicides

S. P. SUMAN and S. C. BAHTEL*

Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur (U. P.)

Manuscript received 29 July 1978, revised 24 November 1978, accepted 22 February 1979

Six 2-arylamino-5-aryl/aryloxy methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles, eight 2-aryl amino-5-aryl/aryloxy methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles, three N₁-aryl/aryloxy acetyl-3,5-dimethyl pyrazoles and three N₁-aryl/aryloxy acetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones have been synthesised with a view to study their antifungal activity. All the compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against '*A. flavus*' and '*A. niger*' and found to be antifungal.

COMPOUNDS containing $\begin{array}{c} | \\ \text{N}-\text{C}-\text{S} \\ | \end{array}$ linkage such as oxadiazoles and thiadiazoles are of versatile biological interest as pesticides and chemotherapeutic agents. Keeping this in view some 2-aryl amino-5-aryl/aryloxy methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles/thiadiazoles have been prepared.

Various substituted pyrazoles and their derivatives have been reported as antibacterials¹⁻⁵, antifungal⁶, insecticidal⁷ and therapeutics⁸⁻¹⁰. With this in view some N₁-aryl/aryloxy acetyl-3,5-dimethyl pyrazoles have been prepared.

Some halogenated and non-halogenated pyrazolones have been screened as fungicides¹¹⁻¹⁴. Working on the generalisation that N-heterocycles incorporated with CO group show significant pesticidal activity, we have prepared N₁-aryl/aryloxy acetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones, which possess an additional CO group directly linked with the pyrazolone ring leading thereby to a possible enhanced activity.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Aryl/Aryloxy Acetyl Hydrazines :

These were prepared by the method of L. Conti¹⁵.

1,4-Disubstituted Thiosemicarbazides :

These were prepared by the method of Paul and Basu¹⁶.

2-Arylamino-5-aryl/aryloxy methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles¹⁶ :

To an ethanolic suspension (300 ml) of 1-aryl/aryloxyacetyl-4-thiosemicarbazide (0.01 M), 4 N. NaOH. (5 ml) was added when a clear solution was obtained on shaking. To this iodine solution (5%) was added dropwise till the color of iodine persisted. The contents were refluxed for two hours, the reaction mixture cooled and poured into ice water (500 ml), the precipitated solid filtered off, washed with water, carbon disulphide and finally recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The oxadiazoles are listed in Table 1.

2-Arylamino-5-aryl/aryloxy methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles¹⁶ :

To 1-aryl/aryloxy acetyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazide (0.01 M), glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was added. To this bromine (0.5 ml) was added dropwise with shaking to a permanent red color. After half an hour the mixture was poured into ice cold water and the solution neutralised with sodium hydroxide. The precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with water and recrystallised. The thiadiazoles thus prepared are listed in Table 2.

N₁-Aryl/aryloxy acetyl-3,5-dimethyl pyrazoles¹⁷ :

To an ethanolic suspension (10 ml) of aryl/aryloxy acetylhydrazine (0.01 M), acetyl acetone (0.01 M) was added and the mixture refluxed for two hours. To this acetic acid (5 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed further for one hour. On evaporation a solid was obtained which was washed and crystallised. The pyrazoles thus prepared are listed in Table 3.

* Lecturer, Department of Chemistry, University of Gorakhpur (U. P.), India.

TABLE 1—2-ARYL AMINO-5-ARYL/ARYLOXY METHYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES

Sl. No.	Name	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N%	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	2- <i>m</i> -Toluidino-5-benzyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole	170	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	15.75	15.85
2.	2- <i>p</i> -Toluidino-5-benzyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole	165	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	15.79	15.85
3 ^a .	2- <i>p</i> -Phenetidino-5-benzyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole	145	30	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	14.13	14.24
4.	2- <i>m</i> -Toluidino-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole	112	35	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂	12.60	12.74
5 ^b .	2- <i>p</i> -Toluidino-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole	100	40	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂	12.62	12.74
6.	2- <i>p</i> -Phenetidino-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole	94	30	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂	11.52	11.68

I.R. Spectral data $\nu_{\max}$ in cm⁻¹

- a. 710 monosubstituted benzene ring ; 830 *p*-disubstituted benzene ring ; 1120 $\begin{array}{c} | \\ -C-O-C- \\ | \end{array}$; 1050, 1245 = $\begin{array}{c} | \\ C-O-C \\ | \end{array}$;
1490—N—H (bending) and 1510 benzene ring.
- b. 725 C—Cl ; 820 *p*-disubstituted benzene ring ; 1070, 1135 $\begin{array}{c} | \\ -C-O-C- \\ | \end{array}$; 1030, 1245 = $\begin{array}{c} | \\ C-O-C \\ | \end{array}$;
1510 benzene ring ; and 1585 —N—H (bending).

TABLE 2—ARYL AMINO-5-ARYL/ARYLOXY METHYL-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLES

Sl. No.	Name	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	N%	
					Found	Calcd.
1 ^c .	2-Anilino-5-benzyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole	106	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	15.60	15.73
2.	2- <i>p</i> -chloroanilino-5-benzyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole	150	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ S	13.85	13.93
3.	2- <i>m</i> -Toluidino-5-benzyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole	173	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	14.86	14.94
4.	2- <i>p</i> -Toluidino-5-benzyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole	185	78	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	14.81	14.94
5.	2- <i>p</i> -Phenetidino-5-benzyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole	144	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	13.34	13.50
6.	2- <i>m</i> -Toluidino-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole	162	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS	12.08	12.15
7 ^d .	2- <i>p</i> -Toluidino-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole	155	74	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS	12.04	12.15
8.	2- <i>p</i> -Phenetidino-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole	158	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	11.01	11.18

I.R. Spectral data $\nu_{\max}$ in cm⁻¹

- c. 715, 755 monosubstituted benzene ring, 1495—N—H (bending) and 1565 benzene ring.
- d. 800 C—Cl ; 810 *p*-disubstituted benzene ring , 1040, 1240— $\begin{array}{c} | \\ C-O-C \\ | \end{array}$ and 1550—N—H (bending).

TABLE 3—N₁-ARYL/ARYLOXY ACETYL-3,5-DIMETHYL PYRAZOLES

Sl. No.	Name	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	N%	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	N ₁ -(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxyacetyl)-3,5-dimethyl pyrazole	105	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₂	10.00	10.05
2 ^e .	N ₁ -(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxyacetyl)-3,5-dimethyl pyrazole	50	63	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	10.78	10.85
3.	N ₁ -Phenylacetyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazole	60	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	12.94	13.08

I.R. Spectral data $\nu_{\max}$ in cm⁻¹

- e. 1060, 1260— $\begin{array}{c} | \\ C-O-C \\ | \end{array}$; 1600 benzene ring ; and 1680, 1650 C=O

TABLE 4— N_1 -ARYL/ARYLOXY ACETYL-3-METHYL-5-PYRAZOLONES

Sl. No.	Name	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	N%	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	N_1 -(4'-Chloro-3'-methoxyphenoxyacetyl)- 3-methyl-5-pyrazolone	170	60	$C_{11}H_{11}ClN_2O_3$	9.87	9.98
2.	N_1 -(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxyacetyl)- 3-methyl-5-pyrazolone	130	55	$C_{14}H_{15}N_2O_3$	10.71	10.77
3 ^f .	N_1 -Phenylacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone	105	68	$C_{15}H_{15}N_2O_3$	12.80	12.96

I.R. Spectral data ν_{max} in cm^{-1}

f. 720, 770 monosubstituted benzene ring ; 1580 benzene ring and 1720 C=O

N_1 -Aryl/aryloxy acetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones¹⁸ :

To an ethanolic suspension (20 ml) of aryl/aryloxy acetyl hydrazine (0.01 M), ethyl acetate (0.01 M) was added and the mixture refluxed for three hours. On evaporation a solid was obtained which was washed and crystallised. The pyrazolones thus prepared are listed in Table 4.

Fungicidal activity :

All the compounds of Table 1, 2, 3 and 4 were screened for their antifungal activity against 'A. flavus' and 'A. niger' by agar plate technique¹⁹⁻²⁰ at three different concentrations namely, 1 : 1000 ; 1 : 10,000 and 1 : 100,000. All the compounds were found to show antifungal activity, however, compounds containing 4'-chloro-3'-methyl phenoxy methyl group displayed higher fungicidal activity. At the same time compounds of Tables 1 and 2 having *p*-phenetidino group showed higher fungicidal activity than compounds with a toluidino group. Secondly, compounds of Table 2 having sulfur displayed higher fungicidal activity than compounds of Table 1 and pyrazolones (Table 4) having a C=O group were found to be more fungicidal than pyrazoles, while thiadiazoles (Table 2) displayed highest fungicidal activity.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Professor R. P. Rastogi, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur for departmental facilities. One of us (S. P. Suman) is thankful to S. C. S. T. (U. P.) for the award of a J. R. F.

References

- G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 351 ; 1975, **52**, 960.
- C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 985 ; 1976, **53**, 163, 371, 827 ; 1977, **54**, 634.
- A. KABRA, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 989 ; 1977, **54**, 508.
- U. WRZECIONO, *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **84**, 30956t.
- N. N. JOSHI and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 1081.
- F. S. G. SOLIMAN and R. M. SHAFIK, *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **83**, 198164b.
- S. A. AGRIPAT, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, **68**, 29699z.
- E. L. ANDERSON, J. E. CASEY, L. C. GREENE, J. J. JAFFERTY and H. E. REIFF, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, **1**, 259.
- R. H. IRSCHMANN, N. G. STEINBERG, E. F. SCHOENEWALDT, W. J. PALWEDA and MAX. TISCHLER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, **1**, 352.
- J. B. WRIGHT, W. E. DULIN and J. H. MARKILLIE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, **7**, 102.
- C. MATSUMURA and Y. UNEI, *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, **67**, 11452h.
- A. ALLAIS and P. GIRAULT, *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, **72**, 21686e.
- B. NANDA, S. PADMANAVAN, B. TRIPATHI and A. S. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 533.
- A. NAYAK, S. DAS, C. R. MISHRA and A. S. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 485.
- L. CONTI, *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **61**, 4253e.
- B. K. PAUL and U. P. BASU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 1121.
- H. G. GARG and P. P. SINGH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 1141.
- M. WOLF, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, **68**, 49599v.
- J. G. HORSHFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1845, **5**, 357.
- U. S. D. A. Circular No. 198, 1931.